

Evaluating Patients' Satisfaction with the Performance Based Financing Project in Ndop Health District

Author's Details:

¹Sirri Mabella Forbeteh, ²Fabien Sundjo and ³Aloysius Njong

¹Catholic University of Bamenda, Camerron ²University of Buea ³University of Bamenda

Abstract

The emergence of Performance-Based Funding programs is part of comprehensive reform goals that can influence all pillars of the health system. The Performance-Based Financing (PBF) approach has attracted significant attention as a promising intervention for improving health services delivery in low- and middle-income countries. This work, therefore, attempts to evaluate patients' satisfaction, 5 years after the inception of the Performance Based Financing pilot phase, in Ndop Health District using quantitative research design with secondary data from the PBF program for 2012 (with 544 respondents) and 2018 (with 1152 respondents). In order to pursue this objective, use was made of descriptive statistics, and both Chi-square and the Ordinary Least Square regression was used to investigate the hypothesis. The results among others revealed that PBF has a positive influence on nurses' attitude in the Ndop Health District, that Patients' satisfaction depends on the nurse's attitude, waiting time and affordability. Most importantly, we found out that the satisfaction level of patients at the Ndop Health District increased significantly five years after the inception of the PBF in 2012. Policy-wise, we encourage the extension of the PBF programme to other localities, if the increase in patient's satisfaction is sort for.

Keywords: Performance Based Financing, Patient satisfaction, and Ordinary List Square regression.

1. Introduction

The past 15 years have witnessed unprecedented global attention to health challenges in low and middle-income countries (LMICs). In 2015, 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs) were established for 2030. These global goals aim to ensure healthy lives and promote wellbeing for all. Improving health outcomes through efforts to strengthen health systems has become a priority in many LMICs. This improvement often requires substantial changes in the organization and governance of health systems, in the face of limited human and financial resources (Sieleunou et al., 2017).

Contractual arrangements have been suggested as possible tools to this end. Among these, the Performance-Based Financing (PBF) approach has attracted significant attention as a promising intervention for improving health services delivery in LMICs (Sieleunou et al., 2017). Under PBF, health care facilities and health care workers have more autonomy and receive financial resources upon taking measurable actions or achieving predetermined performance targets. The emergence of Performance-Based Funding programs is part of comprehensive reform goals that can influence all pillars of the health system. Currently, more than 30 countries in sub-Saharan Africa alone, have introduced (or are in the process of introducing) PBF approaches in their health systems as indicated by (Sieleunou et al., 2017).

PBF actors during the capitalization workshop in Burundi developed a methodology to facilitate a structured analysis of experiences during a one-week 'capitalization write-shop' (Sieleunou et al., 2017). According to Toonen and Jansen, (2015) health advisors, used this methodology for an assignment from the World Bank. They were asked to identify interesting approaches, experiences and results from the Performance-Based Financing (PBF) programs and projects from Burundi and Cameroon that the World should know about. This was documented and then shared with global audiences. The aim of these write-shops was to facilitate the identification, analysis, and documentation of experiences, practices, lessons learned, and promising experiments in the field of PBF. At the same time, each write-shop also facilitated the participants' knowledge-

sharing amongst each other and critically reflected on each other's experiences – with the ultimate “reward” in delivering a publication produced collaboratively. With the help of the Health advisors, six PBF manuals (Financial Sustainability of PBF, Transparency, and Accountability and PBF and the evolution of Health Service Indicators) were developed by Toonen and Jansen in 2015. These PBF manuals have strengthened analysis and dialogue on PBF implementation in both countries and have also informed dialogue on PBF in other countries. Some are policy papers, some are case studies, and some are articles: PBF and Community Participation, PBF and Public-private Partnership and PBF and Autonomy (Commonwealth, Health 2018).

Several reports and events had provided evidence on the state of the poor health outcomes and health financing thereby raising awareness of the situation (Sieleunou et al., 2017). As a result, decision-makers identified the lack of a suitable health financing policy as an important issue that needed to be addressed. The change in the political discourse toward more accountability made room to test new mechanisms. A group of policy entrepreneurs from the World Bank, through numerous forms of influence (financial, ideational, network and knowledge-based) and building on several ongoing reforms, collaborated with senior government officials to place the PBF program on the agenda. The policy changes occurred as a result of two open policy windows (i.e., national and international), and in both instances, policy entrepreneurs were able to couple the policy streams to effect change (Sieleunou et al., 2017).

In Cameroon, the burden of health care financing is largely borne by households, and risk pooling mechanisms are quasi inexistent. The limited public resources allocated to health do not seem to be deployed where they are the most needed. As a result, substantial disparities exist in health outcomes between rural and urban areas, as well as across socioeconomic groups, hereby perpetuating poverty and vulnerability (Hayriye et al., 2013).

Performance-Based Financing in the health sector report, UNICEF and the World Bank has prepared with the Ministry of Public Health a joint funding strategy for the Performance-Based Financing in the health sector. They were committed to addressing health indicators; severe acute malnutrition, poor and vulnerable, children completely vaccinated Ante-Natal services and outpatient consultation just to name a few. Performance-Based Financing is a health system management tool designed to increase the efficiency of health system inputs and to improve the coverage and quality of priority maternal and child health services by paying health facilities bonuses linked to the quantity and quality of services delivered. In order to directly link payments and funding at the provider level with the quantity and quality of health services performed, Cameroon started a Performance Based Financing pilot in the health sector in 2012 in fourteen districts in three regions of the country: East, South West, and North West) (World Bank Group 2018). In the North West region, the project was implemented in four health districts namely: Nkambe, Foundong, Kumbo East and Ndop.

In 2009, the Ministry of Public Health in Cameroon, working in partnership with the World Bank, funded the Cameroon Health Sector Support Investment Project. The five-year US\$25 million initiative was designed to support the provision of key maternal and child health services through Performance-Based Financing (World Bank Group, 2014). This shows that much money had been invested in the project. The main concern of this work is to determine if the investment pumped into this project is worthwhile. With Ndop being one of the pilot districts in the NWR, this study is therefore imperative to investigate if this project has influenced patients' satisfaction level with the health services 5 years after the inception of the project in the Ndop health district.

In the light of the above background, the key question that arises is: What is the patients' level of satisfaction with the health services provided, five years after the inception of the PBF pilot phase, in the Ndop Health District?

Specifically:

- What is the influence of the PBF project on health workers' attitude?

- What are the determinants of patients' satisfaction in the Ndop Health District?
- What is the difference in patient satisfaction before and after the PBF project?

Following the above major question, the main objective, of this paper is to investigate the level of satisfaction of patients following the inscription of the PBF program at the Ndop health district.

Specifically, this study aimed to:

- Investigating the influence of the PBF program on health workers' attitude.
- I am investigating the determinants of patient's satisfaction in Ndop health district.
- I am comparing the level of patients' satisfaction with health care services at inception and 5 years after in Ndop health district.

The rest of this paper will be presented thus: section two will deal on the literature review, section three will focus on the methodology, section four will highlight issues related to the findings and interpretation then section five will present the policy implication, and section six will conclude the paper.

2. Literature Review

As a concern, the Influence of the PBF Project on Health Workers' Attitude the literature is not unanimous. Jensen et al. (2017) carried out a study on the health worker crisis using qualitative design and found out that, current attempt to address the crisis is likely to be insufficient due to lack of sustainable funding for health systems and binding international rules to adequately address the root causes of health worker migration. They went further to explain why health workers often move from rural to urban and from poorer to less poor areas, as well as from the public to the private sector or to programmes funded by donor organizations and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). In many poorer countries, the problem is further exacerbated by international health worker migration, typically from poorer countries in the Global South to wealthier countries in the Global North (Jensen et al., 2017).

Furthermore, a study was carried out on how Performance Based Financing empowers health workers delivering prevention of vertical transmission of HIV services and decreases the desire to leave in Mozambique. Their objectives were to describe the implementation of the PBF intervention and second, to assess the impact of the PBF on health worker motivation, key factors in the workplace environment, health worker satisfaction, and thoughts of leaving. The results showed delayed disbursement of incentives and poor timing of evaluation relative to incentive disbursement. This study looked at the influence of health workers in influencing delivering of vertical transmission of HIV services; meanwhile, the current study evaluates health workers influence on health services (Schuster et al., 2017).

In addition, Jan and Marjolein (2006) explored a study on improving health worker performance. The aim of the study was improving job satisfaction by addressing working conditions, providing incentives and offering professional development. Poor performance is a result of health staff not being sufficient in numbers, or not providing care according to standards, and not being responsive to the needs of the community and patients. Various factors influencing staff retention and mobility can be distinguished: personal and lifestyle-related factors, including living circumstances, work-related factors, related to preparation for work during pre-service education, health-system related factors, such as human resources policy and planning and job satisfaction influenced by health facility factors, such as financial considerations, working conditions, management capacity and styles, professional advancement and safety at work.

Again, Rudasingwa and Uwizeye (2017) looked at physician and nurses' attitude towards performance Based Financial incentives in Burundi: a qualitative study in the province of Gitega. Their objective was to elicit physicians' and nurses' experiences and views on how PBF influenced and helped them in healthcare delivery. They used a qualitative cross-sectional study was carried out among frontline health workers such as physicians and nurses. They discovered that the PBF scheme had provided a positive motivation to improve the quality of care; mainly in the structure and process of care. Their results showed that PBF scheme had provided positive motivation to improve the quality of care, mainly in the structures and process of care. The findings of this study also indicate that the positive interaction between performance-based incentive schemes and other health policies is crucial in achieving comprehensive improvement in healthcare delivery.

As a concern, the determinant of patient satisfaction Schoenfelder et al. (2011) identifies key determinants of patient satisfaction. Data used were obtained through a self-administered, post-visit questionnaire by random sampling during the period of January 2009 to September 2009. The results of the analysis showed that there are 10 determinants of global patient satisfaction. The outcome of treatment was overall, the most salient predictor followed by nursing kindness as the second most important component. The results also indicate that some aspects of the hospital stay are not seen as relevant by patients and therefore are unrelated to satisfaction ratings. The present study will test more than ten determinants of patient satisfaction to come out with its results.

In addition, Batbaatar et al. (2017) systematically identify and review evidence regarding determinants of patient satisfaction between 1980 and 2014, and seek the reasons for contradicting results in relationships between determinants and patient satisfaction in the literature to design a further robust measurement system for patient satisfaction. They used a systematic review guideline of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) statement. They included 109 articles for the synthesis and in their study, they found out that health care service quality indicators were the most influential determinants of patient satisfaction across the studies. Among them, health providers' interpersonal care quality was the essential determinant of patient satisfaction. Socio demographic characteristics were the most varied in the review. The strength and directions of associations with patient satisfaction were found inconsistent. Therefore, person-related characteristics should be considered to be the potential determinants and confounders simultaneously.

Further, Bulut et al. (2014) conducted a study to determine the level of satisfaction of patients utilizing first-level health care facilities as a function of health system performance rating in Elazig province of Turkey. They collected data using a cross-sectional study conducted with 1,290 patients. They concluded that there is a statistically significant difference between the patients' demographic characteristics (sex, educational status, occupation, and income status) and their levels of satisfaction with the family medicine practice. In Pakistan, Maliha et al. (2013) found out that, patient satisfaction with health care services was identified in the literature review, more with private hospitals as compared to public hospitals and health care providers. Patient experiences and their expectations with health care services were found to be an important determinant of patient satisfaction in Pakistan. Young age, female gender, literacy, and high social class are few patient characteristics influencing the level of patient satisfaction. In addition, lack of privacy, autonomy involvement in decision making, poor communication, and sanitation/hygiene leads to bad patient experience hence decreased satisfaction.

Again, a study was explored on Critical Social Determinants of Patients' Satisfaction in Busia County Referral Hospital, in Kenya by Martin et al. (2016). The study was aimed to assess the levels and individual determinants of client satisfaction with outpatient healthcare services at Busia County Referral Hospital using a cross-sectional study. Systematic random sampling method was used to attain a sample of 400 respondents. A pre-tested structured questionnaire was used to conduct interviews. Approximately 84% of the respondents reported being satisfied with outpatient healthcare services. Age of the respondents, place of residence, gender and marital status emerged as significant predictors of general outpatient satisfaction ($p < 0.05$). The study concludes

and recommends that although the majority of respondents reported satisfaction with outpatient healthcare services, the hospital service providers should work hard, to win the interests of the patients and have an environment that better fits the expectations of all patients regardless of their age, gender, marital status, and place of residence.

Thompson and Sunoi (1995) carried out a study on expectations as determinants of patient satisfaction. Their aim was to condense a review of the various approaches to conceptualizing expectations, in relation to user satisfaction, from the perspective of several relevant disciplines in the health and social sciences. In order to do this, they review the recent articles and books from the main contributory disciplines of psychology, sociology, social policy, health care services and management, and marketing. Thompson and Sunois' results of the study showed that acute in-patient expectations are strongly related to satisfaction on some dimensions, by 14% of the variation in satisfaction with nursing care, 17% of food and physical facilities and 6% of medical care and information.

As a concern, the review on patient satisfaction level, Sforzin et al. (2009) carries out a study to quantify the satisfaction level of those that use the Home Care Services of the Trento District. 122 patients that received care by the nursing services of the territory and that received home care at least twice a week, were enrolled in the survey. The responses that emerged from this sample of patients, concerning the satisfaction level, were very positive. Each aspect had a high satisfaction percentage that was always beyond 75%. However, the sample size of this study is 122 patients who are too small to ascertain patient satisfaction level while that of the current study will be 1696.

In addition, Roxane and Dufrene (2000) evaluated a southern medical center's External Patient Satisfaction Survey instrument for validity and reliability and provided a basis that providers might use routinely and systematically to assess the quality of medical care. Patient reports about their medical care can be an important component of quality assessment of medical services. This report is different from the current study in that it evaluated instruments that can be used to assess patient satisfaction while the present study evaluates patients' satisfaction level. Moreover, Luthy et al. (2017) performed a prospective quasi-experimental controlled study measuring the effect of two approaches on patient satisfaction. During three months, 3 wards of a 6 ward medical rehabilitation division were implemented, and 3 control wards kept their usual organization of rounds. In total, 90 patients of each group were included in the study. They came out with a conclusion that; ward rounds influenced the patient-healthcare professionals' encounter. These rounds were associated with improved patient satisfaction with care, particularly regarding interprofessional collaboration and discharge planning. They used a prospective design to come out with their results while the current study will use explanatory research design.

Further, an assessment of patient satisfaction with the services provided in hospitals affiliated to Tehran University of Medical Sciences was explored by Makarem (2016). He identified areas of patient dissatisfaction, and find ways to improve patient satisfaction with hospital services. Using the Satisfaction Survey tool, information of patient's demographic characteristics was collected, and patient satisfaction with 15 areas of hospital services and the intent to return the same hospitals was assessed. The mean score of overall satisfaction with hospital services was 16.86 out of 20. It was found that 58% of participants were highly satisfied with the services provided. The current study intends to assess patient satisfaction with health care services in a district hospital.

A study was carried out on patient care experiences and perceptions of the patient-provider by Tabler et al. (2014). They explored how patients' experiences at 10 primary care clinics influenced their perceptions of their relationship with their primary care providers. Focus group interviews with 63 participants indicated that patients' experiences in the clinics, such as wait-times, influenced perceptions of the patient-provider

relationship. Here the focus is on the patient –provider relationship while the current study focuses on patient satisfaction with health care services.

Research was tested on a new theory of patient satisfaction with treatment outcome. The objective of the study was to test a new theory linking patient satisfaction and embodiment (body–self unity) and examine it in relation to other competing theories. Satisfaction with treatment outcome approximately 4 months after surgery were examined against the following factors (representing 7 theories of satisfaction): 1) overall clinical outcome, 2) patients' a priori self-selected important clinical outcomes, 3) foresight expectations, 4) hindsight expectations, 5) psychologic state, 6) psychologic state in those with poor outcomes, and 7) embodiment. Their results showed that satisfaction with treatment outcome was significantly associated with an embodiment. This study aimed at testing a new theory on patient satisfaction while the current evaluates patient satisfaction level (Hudak et al., 2004).

Oyoo (2015) review patient satisfaction at comprehensive care centers points-of-care in level 5 public health facilities in Kenya. The purpose of this study was to assess patients' satisfaction with HIV/AIDS services at the level 5 comprehensive care centers. Three hundred and ninety (390) patients were interviewed using a questionnaire that consisted of three sections: - socio-demographic characteristics; service quality (SERVQUAL) and Patient Reported Outcome. The study findings showed that the average service score gap for all patients was -0.42, indicating that the expectations were higher than perceptions. There was a positive relationship ($r = 0.699$, or 69.9 %) between the service quality and patient's satisfaction. This study evaluated patient satisfaction only in a public hospital; meanwhile the current evaluate in both private and public hospitals.

3. Methodology

This study will use the quantitative research design. This method is appropriate because it tests the relationship between patient satisfaction and other factors. This method being one of the quantitative approaches to research is useful for testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables. Using this design enables the variables to be measured, typically on instruments, so that numerical data can be analysed using statistical procedures (Creswell, 2008). The population of the Ndop health district is the population of interest in this work. The target population is an adult age 12 and above living in Ndop health district. In addition, the data of the Ndop health district targets males, females, and children in the Ndop health areas.

As concern the source of data, we used secondary data in this study, collected by CBOs for community verification. A total of 1696 questionnaires were used; 544 questionnaires in 2012 and 1152 questionnaires in 2018. The validity of the research instruments was evaluated for face and content validity. To ensure the content validity of the questionnaire, it was reviewed and approved by some World Bank experts, and any misunderstandings were corrected to ease respondents filling. It also ensured that the content of the questions tied directly to the respective expectations of each of the variables. Face validity ensured that the ink, font size, and color of ink and paper were friendly to the respondents.

Model Specification

Following our objectives we specify a general functional equation of the form:

$$PS = f(PBF, AGE, NA, T, OF, C, G) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Following this general functional notation, we further specified the econometric equation as $PS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PBF + \beta_2 AGE + \beta_3 NA + \beta_4 T + \beta_5 OF + \beta_6 C + \beta_7 G + \varepsilon \dots \dots (2)$

Where: PS = patient satisfaction

β_0 =constant term
 PBF=performance Based Financing
 AGE=age of respondents
 NA= Nurse Attitude
 T= time
 OF =affordability
 C=cost of service
 G= Gender
 ε =error term

Where $\beta_0, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6,$ and β_7 the coefficients associated with the independent variables are: performance Based Financing, age of respondents, Nurse Attitude, time, affordability, cost of service and Gender respectively.

Method of Data Analysis

To analyse our data, we, first of all, represented the data using descriptive statistics and charts. We went ahead to do a chi-square by categorizing our data into satisfied (5-10) and not satisfied (1-4) to give a global view of the data collected on the field. However, since this was not the original form of our dependent variable, for a perfect result, we went ahead to run the multiple regression analysis which is best suited for a model whose dependent variable is continuous (1-10).

4. Findings and Interpretations

Presentation of Chi Square Results

Table 1: Results on the Relationship between Patient Satisfaction and Nurse Attitude.

NURSES' ATTITUDE			
Year (2012)	(426) 25.1%	(118)7.0%	544 (32.1%)
Year (2018)	(1080) 63.7%	(72) 4.2%	1152 (67.9%)
X^2			0.083

Source: Computed by authors using SPSS. 17

Looking at the results of nurses attitude and the PBF project, we see that more nurses had a good attitude (63.7%) in 2018 (5 years after the inception of PBF) than at the inception of the project in 2012(25.1%). Results on table 1 also show that there is a statistically significant association ($X^2 = 0.083$) between Total patients Satisfaction and the different nurse attitude at a 10% level of significance. This means that the patient's satisfaction was associated with nursing attitude.

Table 2: Regression Results for Patients Satisfaction by Policy and Other Determinants

Variables	B	Std. Error	P-VALUE
(Constant)	3.883	0.264***	0.000
Policy	0.606	0.053***	0.000
Age	0.001	0.002	0.646
Nurse attitude	1.606	0.258***	0.000
Waiting Time	1.679	0.092***	0.000
Affordability	0.937	0.065***	0.000
Log cost	-0.008	0.020	0.671
Recoded Gender	-0.312	.051***	0.000
F-statistics	230.371		0.000
Adjusted R-square	0.384		

Source: computed by authors using SPSS. 17

Table 2 above validates our objective 2 which is that of looking for the determinants of patient's Satisfaction in the Ndot Health District. From the table below, it can be seen that AGE has a positive coefficient (.001). This means that an increase in Age by one unit, say one year, will lead to an increase in Total patient Satisfaction Level by 0.001. This result is however statistically insignificant even at 10% level of significant (P-value= 0.65).

We can also observe a positive coefficient for nurses' attitude (1.606), indicating that an improvement in Nurses' Attitude will increase total client's satisfaction level by 1.606. This result is statistically significant at a 1% level (P-value = 0.000). With the variable TIME, it is also seen that it has a positive coefficient (1.679). This shows that the patient's satisfaction is higher with a shorter waiting time compared to the long waiting time. This result is statistically significant at a 1% level (P-value = 0.000).

The variable 'affordability' also has a positive coefficient (.937) revealing that clients who found the costs of health services to be affordable were more satisfied with health services than those who found it not to be affordable. Those who found the services to be affordable were more satisfied than those who found it unaffordable by 0.937. This result is statistically significant at a 1% level (P-value = 0.000).

The coefficient of Log of Cost is negative z (-0.008), meaning a percentage increase in the cost of healthcare will lead to a fall in Total Satisfaction Level by 8% (.008* 100). This result is not statistically significant even at 10% Level of significance (P-value = .671). The Sex has a negative coefficient (-.312). This means that women had a lower satisfaction level than men, and this result was statistically significant at a 1% level (P-value = 0.000).

The table above also validates our objective three which is that of comparing patient's satisfaction at inception and 5 years after the inception of the PBF policy can be validated. It can be seen that the coefficient of PBF is positive (0.610). This means with the introduction of PBF (Performance Based Finance) policy, patients' satisfaction level was higher 5 years (2018) later than at its inception (2012), by 0.61. This result is statistically significant at a 1% level of significance, with a P-value = 0.000.

5. Policy Recommendations

PBF

The project should be applicable in all the 10 regions in Cameroon. This is because of the benefits of the project achieved in the North West region like the present study that has proven that PBF has an influenced-on patient satisfaction level. PBF has improved on the infrastructure, rehabilitation and has put in place standard medical equipment which facilitates the process and quality of health care delivery. The project has also increased the utilization of health care services by providing funds to subsidize some health care services and medical drugs. It also has a positive influence on nurse attitude which has definitely boosted up utilization of health care services.

The project should continue until further notice. This is because the project has significantly improved on the quality and quantity of health care services and this has led to a positive increase in patients' perception.

In addition, the project targets especially the poor and vulnerable by providing equity bonuses to carter for their health needs, and since they are paupers in all communities, the project should continue so that they scan also benefit from free health services. Moreover, it should continue in order to reduce the rate at which people die in their homes because they cannot afford health care services or do not have access to the health care centers.

Reinforce supervision of health services in order to improve on the quality of services rendered to the community and also to increase the rate of transparency in the health institutions.

Nurse attitude

Health workers should be motivated irrespective of their pay packages. This will prompt them to give in their best in quality and quantity. Qualitatively, services rendered to the population will be of standard and quantitatively, health personnel will work additional hours when the need arises without any push or fear of penalty from the hierarchy.

They should be informed about what the community thinks about them in order to improve in areas of weaknesses. This is because no one is perfect and sometimes one might offend another unnoticed. Therefore, if community perception is made accessible, medical personnel will improve in the area of their weaknesses with good faith.

They should constantly be educated on how to relate with patients by organizing monthly seminars on nurse - patient relationship among the staff so that experiences will be shared and thus will serve as a learning process. This will also help those who must have forgotten what was taught in school and will also confirm the saying that goes that theory is different from practical.

Affordability

Prices of drugs and services should be subsidized by other health programs so that the patients can effectively buy essential drugs prescribed in the pharmacy. This will help eliminate the practice of patients buying drugs from illegal sources and will go as far as preventing the effects of these unauthorized drugs on the individual.

Supervision should be intensified by pasting the price list on the window or door of the pharmacy so that patients can verify their bills in case of any doubts. Supervision will also help increase the level of transparency in the health facility.

Doctors should prescribe essential drugs in the hospital pharmacy which are cheaper to afford. This will help reduce the expenses of the patient on like going to the private pharmacy where these same drugs will be sold at a very high price. It will also help the patient save time so as to go home and have some rest that can lead to a quick recovery.

Waiting time

Patients should be entertained with modern electronics in the waiting hall. This is because waiting time is one of the determinants of patient satisfaction and no health institution will want patients to visit their health center and leave unsatisfied. Entertainment will prevent the patient from being lonely but follow the cue patiently until when he or she will be seen by the doctor.

Doctors should not teach student doctors during ward rounds; rather they should note their worries to be clarified in the doctors' office. Answering questions posed by student doctors or teaching students during ward rounds take much time thus prolonging the number of hours spent on that activity. Doctors are therefore called upon to entertain questions from students afterward rounds.

More nurses and doctors should be recruited. As the saying goes that more hands do light work, the health management committee should recruit more nurses and doctors so that patients will not stay too long in hospitals or health centers.

6. Conclusion

This work aimed at investigating the influence of PBF on health workers' attitude, comparing the determinants of patient satisfaction and evaluating patient satisfaction level five years (2018) after the inception (2012) of PBF. In order to do this, we used secondary data by taking questionnaires from the PBF office collected by CBOs from the field. The method used to analyse the data was chi-square and OLS which brings out the test of dependence that there is a significant relationship between PBF and nurse attitude. This means satisfaction depends on the nurse attitude. We also used the OLS estimate technique to analyse the data effectively. This tool was used because of its Blue property to compare the level of patient satisfaction.

The study finds out that, there exists a statistically significant difference in patient satisfaction 5 years after the PBF pilot phase in Ndop health district thus rejecting the null hypothesis which says there exists no statistical difference in patient satisfaction 5 years after the PBF pilot phase in Ndop health district and accepting the alternative. Thus, we conclude that there is a significant change in patient satisfaction level after the inception of the Performance Based Financing project in Ndop health district. This, therefore, means that PBF has a positive influence on patient satisfaction level in Ndop health district.

References

- i. Batbaatar, E; Javkhlanbayar, D; Ariunbat; L. (2017). *Determinants of patient satisfaction a systematic review. Journal of Sage, Vol. 137(2), pp.89-101.*
- ii. Bell, M. (1995). *Bell object relations Inventory for Adolescents and children Reliability, Validity and Factorial Invariance. Journal of personality assessment, Vol. 80. pp19-25.*
- iii. Bulut, A. and AFerdaneO. (2014). *Evaluating the level of satisfaction of patients utilizing first-level health facilities as a function of health system performance rating in the province of Elazig Turkey. Journal Dove press, Vol. 8, pp. 1483—1492.*
- iv. World, B. (2018). *Cameroon Performance Based Financing, Impact evaluation report. Vol1, pp. 96. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/756781499432127674>*
- v. Commonwealth, H. (2018). *Commonwealth Health Ministers Meeting report. [http://thecommonwealth.org/media/event/commonwealth-health-ministers-meeting-2018.](http://thecommonwealth.org/media/event/commonwealth-health-ministers-meeting-2018)*
- vi. Creswell, J. (2008). *Research Design, A qualitative and quantitative research methods. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/305215626>*
- vii. Hayriye, I. and Hubert N. (2013). *Health care system and health financing structure the case of Cameroon. Journal of Anatoua Academic Conline, Vol. 1(2) pp. 24-44.*
- viii. Hudak, P; Sheilah H; Claire B; Patricia, M. and James, W. (2004). *Testing a new theory of patient satisfaction with treatment outcome. Vol. 42 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4640811?seq>.*
- ix. Jan, H. and Marjolein, D. (2006). *Improving health worker performance. Vol. 11(8), pp.1303-1317. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/255653690_*
- x. Jensen, N. (2013). *The health worker crisis: an analysis of the issues and the main international responses. Journal of poverty Action, Vol. 14 (2), pp. 345- 546.*
- xi. Maliha, N. and Babar, S. (2012). *Determinants of patient's satisfaction with health care system in Pakistan. Journal of Public Health, Vol. 2(2), pp.52-61.*
- xii. Makarem, J. (2013). *Patients' satisfaction with inpatient services provided in hospitals affiliated to Tehran University of Medical Sciences Iran during PMCID. PMC4958929, Vol. 9. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27471589>*
- xiii. Martin, M. (2016). *Critical Social Determinants of Patients' Satisfaction in Busia County Referral Hospital Kenya. Vol. 6, pp.185-190. [http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/.](http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)*
- xiv. Oyoo, T. (2015). *Patient satisfaction at comprehensive care centers points-of-care in level 5 public health facilities in Kenya. <https://ir-library.ku.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/123456789/14276/>*

- xv. *Sieleunou, I; Jean C; Taptue F; Turcotte-T. and Valery R. (2017). Setting performance-based financing in the health sector agenda: a case study in Cameroon. Journal of Globalization and Health, Vol. 13(1), pp.52.*
- xvi. *Schuster, R; Octaviode, S; Kathe R; Carolyn V; David, P; Lynn, J; Mduduzi, M; Delphine, P. and Seral, Y. (2017). PBF empowers health workers delivering prevention of vertical transmission of HIV services and decreases desire to leave in Mozambique. Journal of health policy and management, Vol. 7(7), pp.630-644.*
- xvii. *Schoenfelder, T. Joachim, K. and Jorg K. (2011). Determinants of Patient Satisfaction, A Study among 39 Hospitals in an In-Patient Setting in Germany. Journal for Quality in Health Care, Vol. 38. PP. 357.*
- xviii. *Sforzin, S; Assistenza, P; Azienda, P. and Servizi, S. (2009).Evaluation of patients' satisfaction of home care services.Journal of National Library of Medicine, Vol, (2), pp.135-45.*
- xix. *Thompson, T. and Sunoi W. (1995). Expectations as determinants of patients satisfaction: concepts, theory and evidence. Journal for quality in health care, Vol. 7. pp 127-141.*
- xx. *Toonen, J. and Jansen, C. (2015). Global health. Journal of royal tropical institute. Communication@Kit.nl +31(0)205688711.*
- xxi. *Rudasingwa, M. and Uwizeye, M. (2017). Physician and nurses' attitude towards PBF incentive in Burundi: a qualitative study in the province of Gitega. Journal of Global health Action, Vol.10 (1), pp. 1-64.*
- xxii. *Roxane L, and Dufrene, N. (2000).An evaluation of a patient satisfaction survey validity and reliability. Journal of Elsevier, Vol. 23 pp. 293-300*
- xxiii. *Luthy, C; Patricia, G; Angela P; Valerie P; Francoise A. and Christine C. (2017). Evaluation of patient satisfaction in intensive medical rehabilitation wards. Journal of open access, Vol. 12(2).*